

Potential of Cryogenic Electronics for Future Computing Systems

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Abstract—Cryogenic electronics have great potential to advance computing capabilities and quantum information processing. We explore two categories: Superconducting Electronics (SCE) and Cryogenic semiconductor electronics (Cryo-Semi). Taking advantage of the inherent phenomenon of superconductivity with zero resistance and Josephson junctions, SCE presents notable advantages in energy efficiency, minimal power dissipation, and gigahertz processing speed. Similarly, cryo-semi electronics offers a compelling advantage over their room temperature counterpart; these include lower noise, higher operating speed, increased efficiency, and wide-range operating temperature. Both SCE and cryo-semi exhibit compatibility with quantum technologies and deep space applications. Both have the capacity to operate at deep cryogenic temperatures, making them an appealing candidate for quantum computing. Their integration enables the seamless integration of classical and quantum resources in a shared cryogenic environment, improving quantum error correction and operating temperature compatibility.

Index Terms—Cryogenic electronics, Cryo-CMOS, HPC, Superconductors, Superconducting Electronics, Single-Flux-Quantum, Quantum Computing,

I. INTRODUCTION

In the ever-evolving landscape of computing, the quest for enhanced performance and capabilities continues to push the boundaries of innovation. Cryogenic electronics that operate at extremely low temperatures have garnered significant attention. This growing technology offers promising potential in addressing the challenges of conventional electronic systems, particularly in the context of processing speed, power, and efficiency. As the demands of computing tasks escalate and the limitations of existing technologies become evident, the necessity for novel electronics that can cater to these demands becomes increasingly apparent.

Superconducting digital electronics have achieved major breakthroughs during the last decade that enable the development of superconducting microprocessors through energy-efficient biasing techniques and higher integration [1]. Important properties of superconductors are (i) zero resistance, thus no power dissipation, and (ii) persistent current. The latter allows for supercurrent flows without any loss over time [2].

Single Flux Quantum logic is a digital logic family for superconducting circuits. It operates using the discrete units of magnetic flux called "flux quanta," which are the smallest possible magnetic flux changes allowed in superconducting loops. In SFQ logic, binary information is encoded as the presence or absence of these flux quanta. SFQ logic utilizes

the Josephson junction's ability to switch between two states resistive (state 0) or superconducting (state 1) rapidly and with extremely low energy consumption. The Josephson junction is the key component of superconducting circuits, and exhibits the Josephson effect, enabling the passage of supercurrents through a thin insulating barrier between superconducting materials [3]. SFQ logic has the advantage of ultra-high processing speeds and exceptionally low power consumption, making it suitable for applications in high-performance and low-energy computing, as well as quantum computing systems [4].

Cryogenic semiconductor technology includes operating semiconductor devices at a wide range of low temperatures. Some notable examples of cryo-Semi devices are; (i) Cryo-CMOS (complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor) which are silicon-based devices [5], (ii) cryo-HBTs (Heterojunction Bipolar Transistors) based from gallium arsenide (GaAs) or indium phosphide (InP) [6] and (iii) cryo-HEMTs (High-Electron Mobility Transistors) based from gallium nitride (GaN) [7]. At cryogenic temperatures, electron mobility increases, leading to reduced resistive losses and lower leakage currents. This allows cryo devices to operate with lower power consumption and improved energy efficiency. With reduced scattering and higher electron mobility, transistors can switch faster and operate at higher frequencies, thus enhancing the speed and performance compared to their room-temperature counterparts. Cryogenic temperatures also minimize thermal noise, which can improve the signal-to-noise ratio in electronic circuits. This reduction in noise can lead to more accurate and reliable data processing, especially in sensitive applications like high-resolution imaging and scientific instrumentation [8]. Several works use cryo-CMOS technology to facilitate the integration of CMOS circuitry with superconducting quantum devices. This compatibility is crucial for realizing hybrid classical-quantum systems, where low-noise classical control electronics are required to interact with quantum bits (qubits) [9].

II. HYBRID CLASSICAL-QUANTUM INTERFACE

The integration of hybrid classical and quantum architecture and processing units is envisioned to enable various application algorithms combining quantum and classical modules [10]. The use of classical cryogenic circuits co-located in the same cryostat has the potential to increase the scalability of the quantum system. This can be achieved by replacing

Fig. 1. Cryogenic software-hardware stack

the racks of equipment with embedded cryogenic electronics such as cryo-CMOS and SFQ-based circuits [11] [12]. These technologies enable high-fidelity control, readout, and error correction, while also eliminating the need for bulky coaxial cables that connect from room temperature down to 20 millikelvins. Furthermore, by co-locating classical control and qubits, we can create a low-latency hybrid system that reduces latency between the quantum and classical modules, resulting in an increased speed of information processing. The integrated cryogenic software-hardware stack as shown in Fig.1 refers to the entire software and hardware infrastructure required to control, measure, and interface with quantum devices operating at extremely low temperatures [13].

A. Challenges

Current quantum systems, while promising and groundbreaking, also face several significant challenges that need to be addressed for their widespread adoption and practical use. Quantum states are incredibly sensitive to their surrounding environment, leading to a phenomenon known as decoherence. This results in the loss of quantum information and limits the duration of quantum computations. To mitigate this, quantum error correction techniques are being developed to counteract these effects, but they require additional qubits and complex operations, posing a substantial challenge. Another bottleneck is the cabling density. The on-chip wiring is a challenge due to a number of fan-out and issues on crosstalk. Efficient interconnects over long distances while preserving quantum coherence is a formidable task. Bringing the hardware interface, control, and readout into closer proximity to the QPU will effectively tackle these challenges.

III. VERY LARGE SCALE INTEGRATION

Very large Scale Integration (VLSI) of cryo-CMOS and SFQ circuits will improved component density, cabling, power and enable the scalability of current supercomputers and Quantum computers. However, this requires cryogenic-aware design automation tools, transistor models, and standard cell libraries that are compatible with existing design automation and synthesis flows [14], [15].

IV. CONCLUSION

By harnessing the potentials of superconducting and semiconductor technologies at ultra-low temperatures, this technology has the advantage to enhance performance, energy efficiency, and compatibility with quantum systems. The prospect of achieving unparalleled processing speeds, reduced power consumption, and seamless classical-quantum integration is a significant advantage in developing advanced computing systems. Nevertheless, there remain substantial areas that demand notable improvements.

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